

Open (Web) Search, a booster for Open Science?

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Abstract

Openness, transparency, accessibility and reproducibility are fundamental prerequisites of science. This holds true for all parts of the scientific process and needs to be realised at all organisational levels: for the individual researcher, for universities and academia, for research organisations, for the ‘publication’ of research results as well for societal and general perception and acceptance of scientific findings.

For this reason, open science initiatives promote the general openness of scientific methods, computer-source-code, data, publications, peer-review processes and educational resources. In particular the open access principle to scientific ‘publications’ (often enough meaning a seclusion of scientific results from the public domain in the past, as the copyright for scientific material had to be transferred to the big publishing houses) is of utmost importance, to widely spread, share and debate, and in the end societally accept scientific findings. Similarly, the findability and accessibility of (research-)data is of utmost importance for acceptance and reproducibility of scientific findings.

As ever more information is consumed from and rendered to the public digital sphere - the web – transparent and reproducible finding of information therein is of fundamental importance for science in general. The Open Web Search initiative has identified this need for open and reproducible findability of data and information in the web and is currently building a comprehensive and open web index as a public infrastructure and reference. In particular, if this open web index can be established as a publicly audited and constantly available data base for web resources and if it can be accessed and searched in an open and unbiased manor, it may serve as a significant reference and booster for open science in the long run. A problem that has to be overcome in this regard is that scientific knowledge beyond classical publications is fragmented over many different outlets and in different formats, for example, grey literature, educational resources, datasets, or software tools. Accessibility and discoverability of semantic connections between scientific artefacts in such heterogeneous subsystems can be considered as a limiting factor for innovations.

Thus, novel semantic search mechanisms are needed that allow for browsing the rich landscape of scientific outlets on the web in a more structured, unbiased, and effective

manner, which is not necessarily well supported by current mainstream web search engines.

The German Aerospace Center (DLR) as a large research organisation for space, aeronautics and transportation research in Europe, has identified this issue and has started to work on open search technologies to navigate internal resources such as intranet, code-repositories, Wiki, publication data bases, document repositories synergistically and in a synoptic manor. Furthermore, DLR is also engaging-in and supporting the European Open Web Search initiative by helping to build an open and cooperative web search ecosystem across many different science and computing centres for the Web itself.

In this talk we discuss how DLR is working to improve the synergistic searchability, findability of internal documents, data, publications and computer code in synergy and together with external web resources and web indices generated in the pan European Open Web Search ecosystem, currently under development. This synergistic use of state-of-the-art and innovative open search capacities, by linking DLR-internal and external scientific resources, will provide DLR scientists with up-to-date, objective and unbiased information and will allow its researchers to transparently search and access Web resources for open and reproducible open science. Open (Web) Search is still in an early stage of its development. However, given the ever-increasing informational needs for open and objective science, Open Web Search needs to be implemented at its full potential and in a joint effort of science organisations in the years to come: to support open and transparent sharing of scientific information and to ensure maximum accessibility and acceptance of scientific results in general, by making the scientific process as transparent and reproducible as possible.